

CLINICAL USE OF PLATELET-RICH PLASMA IN CHILDREN AND ADOLESCENTS DIAGNOSED WITH VITILIGO

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ABSTRACT

Vitiligo has a great influence on the psychological state and self-assessment of the patient, especially when the skin of the face and hands is damaged, such patients are more psychically ill, they are diagnosed with various disorders of the psyche.

Vitiligo is a multifactorial disease that develops as a result of a combination of genetic, metabolic and Immunological Disorders. Disruption of melanocyte regeneration and proliferation processes is evidence of defects in these cells.

Platelet-enriched plasma (TBP) is an autological product of blood whose platelet concentration is 3-5 times greater than the normative concentration of platelets in the blood. Currently, there are more than 40 commercial systems for obtaining TBP from intact blood. In most systems, TBP is obtained by double centrifugation. The final concentration of platelets depends not only on the system being used, but also on the presence of a number of individual characteristics of the patient, in particular, his age and the presence of side diseases.

Platelets manifest in themselves, disc-shaped cells, which are deprived of their nucleus and are not capable of independent division. The primary function of platelets is their participation in hemostasis. After injury, platelet activation occurs, as a result of which the cells secrete the composition of granules with growth factors, provoking regeneration processes.

Platelets have three types of granules-Alpha, Delta and Iyambda. The number of Alpha-granules is greatest, with the proportion corresponding to 10% of the total platelet volume. They contain a number of receptors and soluble proteins that break down into the extracellular space when damaged. These proteins modulate inflammatory, hemostasis and cell growth processes. Delta-granules have molecules that trigger hemostasis, including calcium, magnesium, adenosine ions and biologically active amines serotonin and histamine. Laymbda-granules exhibit altered lysosomes in appearance and have a number of enzymes responsible for the degradation of proteins, lipids and carbohydrates.

TBP features are associated with having a number of growth factors secreted by platelets upon activation. In more alpha-granules, the factors present control key cellular

processes, including chemotaxis, mitogenesis and cell differentiation. Growth factors directly trigger the synthesis of the migration of mesenchymal and epithelial cells, their division, collagen and other components of the intercellular Matrix. Interacting with each other, growth factors activate various intracellular signaling pathways that trigger regeneration processes.

The most important growth factors present in TBP are platelet growth factor (PDGF), beta transformative growth factor (TGF- β), vascular endothelium growth factor (VEGF), epidermal growth factor (EGF), insulin-like growth factor (IGF), and fibroblast growth factor (FGF).

Contrary to its name, PDGF is present not only in platelets, but also in monocytes, macrophages, fibroblasts and endothelial cells. This factor triggers fibroblast chemotaxis and mitosis, as well as collagen synthesis and extracellular matrix remodeling. In addition, PDGF triggers macrophage and neutrophil chemotaxis, enhancing TGF- β secretion by macrophages.

TGF - β is a family of factors composed of three isoforms, TGF- β 1, TGF- β 2, and TGF- β 3, and a bone morphogenetic factor. The active form of TGF- β 1 is secreted by platelets in injury, triggering collagen synthesis and preventing its degradation. In addition, TGF- β 1 triggers connective tissue angiogenesis, regeneration, and chemotaxis of various components in the immune system.

VEGF is secreted with activated platelets and macrophages. The main function of this growth factor is the formation of blood-carrying vessels. In addition to VEGF, fibroblast growth factor is responsible for the remodeling process. EGF endotheliocytic chemotaxis, mesenchymal humoral angiogenesis and adhesive mitosis. Ashboob factor Yara yuzalaring epithelization is the main Rolni Bajarishi and regenerative zharaenlar continuationlign ancha crossatilgan storytelling. Bundan tashkent, mesenchymal EGF and hujiralar epithelium tomated cytokinlar sebun secretion.

IFG-1 hormonal background of the ego is a polypeptide visible to this, a plasma normal component of the counter, but it is also present in the platelet junction. The secretion of langand is a mesenchymal factor of differentiation and mitogenesis of fuel. Bundan tashkent, IGF-1 suyakad formation and osteoblast agility differentiation.

FGF eng kuchli mitogenlardan biri, in particular, mesenchymal hudiralar, chondrocytlar and osteoblastlar as the basis of the chondlanadi mitogen. VEGF bilan birga ushbu is a pregnancy-producing factor of jaraenlarin angiogenesis.

TBP neutrophillar and monocytllarni faollashtiruvchi bir a number of cytokinlarni ajratishi tsariga tugma immune reactions, and yalliglanide jaraginin produced by pregnant women and yallaglatiruvchi daraenni daily. Leukocytolarning migraine jaraeniga jawbgar and TBP tomated lanadigan secretion base cytokinlar CXCL7 (NAP-2), PF4 (CXCL4) and CCL5 scallanadi. A criminal case has been opened on this fact, and an investigation is underway. In particular, beta-thromboglobulin isoformazine, known as etuvchi CXCL7 neutrophillary migraine and flammable faollashuvini, inhibiting MONOCYTLARS CCL5 and T-lymphocytlar, eosinophyllar, basophillar, tabium killerlar and dendrite hairalarnollasht. PF4 macrophaglarining against the activity of zharaenin ishga tushiradi, bunking was the result of yallyanishga Karshi and regenerative functions providing Yang functional Feng eg buladi.

This is reported by the press service of the President of the Republic of Tajikistan Emomali Rahmon. Tizza for immunogenic arthritis similida TBP yalliglanish zhavobin produced kilishga kadyrligi kursatilgan.

TBP Dan traumatology, orthopedics and sports medicine eng kulanadi. In particular, the university city is a residential complex of arthroscopic operations performed in TBP. A criminal case has been opened on this fact, and an investigation is underway. 2015-Yilda osteoporosis TBP Bilan Davlata Bravija presented data on ethylgan 3 meta-analysis review of the announcement. TBP affects Bilan kuzatilib's bile, aha kamaishiga syndrome olib kelishi kursatilgan. Meheux C.J. et al. (2016) Nin ishida TBP injections of hyaluronic acid compounds present in the body injections samaraliruk ekanlig crossatilgan. Shunga bishshash natijalar Smith P.A. (2016) Nin yirik randomlashtirilgan research olindi. During the conversation, the parties expressed satisfaction with the development of cooperation between Tajikistan and China, as well as the development of cooperation between Tajikistan and China.

Filardo G. et al. (2010) Nin research tizza Kulyab horticulture tendinitin davolashda TBP injection mining samaradorligi kursatilgan. A criminal case has been opened on this fact, and an investigation is underway.

Regeneration jaraenlarida participates in this tour of omillaring keng spectrum thanks to TBP Dan surunkali yaralarni davolashda foidalaniladi. In particular, the trophic and diabetic yaralarda TBP Nin Yukori samaradorligi kurzatilgan.

Obolensky V.N. and Ermolova D.A. (2012) Nin ishlarida TBP ni turli etiologiali suruncal trophic yaralarni davolashda davlatsh tashribasiga definition of bergan. TBP Dan foidalanib whitecasilgan sadamlar effective course of 66.7% of patients yaraning prolonged epithelialization of the erishildi type.

Shtutin A.A. and bask. (2016) the old-fashioned peripheral botanist zharomatdan Keying is his long-time neuropathyasin, as is TBP mehribasiga Berishdi's definition. Peri-endoneurolysis of bintkazyrganidan keyin TBP epineuricasing infiltration of olib borildi. The author is currently the result of neurodegenerative jaraenlarning by sezilarli Darajada thesaurus reports berishdi.

Boldyreva O.V. and bashkir (2016) suruncal atrophic pharyngitis davolash ikun TBP Dan foidalanish tashribasiga definition of berishdi. Author, TBP larynx schillitz, local microcirculatory apparatus, unda Regeneration jaraenlarining faollashuvini chursatishdi.

Dermatologyada TBP Dan uyali alopecia davolas as foidalaniladi. During the meeting, the sides discussed issues of cooperation between Tajikistan and China.

Ilyada, the literary critic of TBP, and his long-standing vitiligos appeared as a long-lasting work. Shu Tarika, Ibrahim Z.A. et al. (2016) Ning Research turgun vitiligo there are 60 patients involved in etdi. Each patient suffers from injuries related to the absence of symptoms, which can lead to deterioration of health and deterioration of health status. The result of uygunlashgan was given by the pigmentation group of statistical significance, precisely determined by aishshilanandi.

Abdelghani R. et al. (2017) olib borgan Research segment on vitiligo there are 80 patients involved in ETDI. Davolash Hospital sadlik methodology approach 4 groups: carbonate anhydride laser bilan therapy, TBP injections, carbonate anhydride laser and TBP injections, shuningdek carbonate anhydride laser and ingichka UB-nurlanish therapy

uygunliga. It lasted 2 years. Eng aishhi natijalar TBP injections of bilan uygunlikda laser therapy reception of kilgan paciflora guru olindi.

Shundai kilib literary studies analysis of moles, vitiligo complex pathogenesis, davolashga complex yondashuvni requires etuvchi, monitoring the development of bottlenecks.

Currently, there is a dumb dori-darmon, a surgeon or a davolashning physicist trying to apply the method, but it is also necessary to use the following results. Vitiligon Eng crackaligan phototherapy is considering mold control, but literary therapy has a long-term risk of developing the disease.

Dori-darmon therapy bir train preparatlar, immunosuppressor bridge locale or tizimli foidalanilishin from ichiga oladi. A group of corticosteroid drugs, including intravenous injections in the form of emas, topical or intrauterine tizim for pregnant women.

Vitiligon jarrokhli Bilan davolash is a method of installment of long-term and necessary options. During the entire duration of the transplant, the practitioner fined the college certain skills that require this, for a long time the collective labor manager as a specialist, requiring the uskun and labor skill ethic. Shu bilan birga cultivationlanmagan Houghaira outdoor transplants for the treatment of problematic climate requires this medicine.

Vitiligon davolashning Yang methodlari found bürlmoqda and ulard eng hibollis plateletlar bilan boytilgan plasma therapy on the bills. Currently, there are many methods to improve the quality of products. In this study, vitiligon gave an adjective as an independent method, it has also been attempted to assess the effectiveness and safety of TBP injection in harmony with other methods of therapy for this disease.

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